

SYNTHESIS OF COUMARINS FROM PHENOLS AND ACETOACETIC ESTERS. CONSTITUTION OF HALOGENATED RESORCINS AND ORCINS.

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The condensation of halogenated and negatively substituted phenols with β -ketonic esters forming substituted coumarins (Chakravarti and Ghosh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 12, 622) has furnished a ready means for determining the constitution of the substituted phenols. The present investigation was undertaken with a view to determine the constitution of bromoresorcins and the chloro- and bromo-orcins.

Two bromoresorcins, evidently 4-bromo- and 2-bromoresorcins, are described in literature and they have been prepared in the following way (*cf.* Zehenter, *Monatsh.*, 1887, 8, 293; Hemmelmayr, *ibid.*, 1914, 35, 1):

On condensation with acetoacetic ester in presence of sulphuric acid (Pechmann's reaction) these bromoresorcins would form either 7-hydroxy-6-bromo-4-methylcoumarin (I) or 7-hydroxy-8-bromo-4-methylcoumarin (II). These coumarins have, therefore, been synthesised by a method which leaves no doubt about their constitution. 8-Nitro-7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin, the nitration product of β -methylumbelliferone (Chakravarti and Ghosh,

J. Indian Chem. Soc., 1935, **12**, 791), on reduction with stannous chloride and hydrochloric acid gives 8-amino derivative, which forms a stable diazo-anhydride and the latter on treatment with cuprous bromide in hydrobromic acid gives (II). Similarly 6-nitro- β -methylumbelliferone-methyl ether, obtained by the nitration of the methyl ether of β -methylumbelliferone (*cf.* Chakravarti and Banerjee, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1937, **14**, 37) gives the methyl ether of (I).

The preparation of bromoresorcins, however, has been attended with practical difficulties. The bromoresorcin of Zehenter (*loc. cit.*) could not be obtained by following the experimental conditions recorded by him and it has been prepared by a modification of the method (*vide experimental*). It readily undergoes Pechmann's condensation with acetoacetic ester and alkyl acetoacetic esters forming coumarins. The coumarin derived from this bromoresorcin and acetoacetic ester has been found to give a methyl ether (m.p. 245°), which is identical with the methyl ether of (I) and is, therefore, 6-bromo-7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin and the bromoresorcin from which it is derived is, therefore, 4-bromoresorcin. Attempts to prepare the second bromoresorcin by the method described in literature failed. The synthesis of 2-bromoresorcin by other methods was not successful. In attempting to synthesise 2-bromoresorcin by brominating the disulphonic acid of resorcin and then removing the sulphonic groups by steam distillation (*cf.* preparation of 2-nitroresorcin, Kaufmann and Pay, *Ber.*, 1904, **37**, 716) it has been found that excess of bromine produces tribromoresorcinol (m.p. 111°) with the replacement of the sulphonic groups. But if one molecule of bromine is used for the bromination of resorcin-disulphonic acid, then after passing superheated steam at 180°, 4-bromoresorcin is obtained instead of 2-bromoresorcin. That the bromoresorcin, thus obtained, is 4-bromoresorcin is proved by the condensation with acetoacetic ester forming (I), (m.p. 278°) identical with the coumarin obtained from bromoresorcin derived from β -resorcylic acid. The troublesome method of preparing 4-bromoresorcin from resorcylic acid may be conveniently replaced by this less cumbrous method and the yield is also satisfactory in this case,

The halogenated orcins, e.g. monochloro-orcine and monobromo-orcine have also been prepared and their constitution determined by the formation of substituted coumarins from them.

(a) *Monochloro-orcine* has been prepared by the action of the calculated quantity of sulphuryl chloride on a dry ethereal solution of orcin. Excess of sulphuryl chloride leads to the formation of polychlorinated derivatives.

(b) *Monobromo-orcine* was prepared by Lamparter (*Annalen*, 1865, 134, 258) by the action of bromine water on orcin but it has now been very conveniently prepared by passing a slow stream of carbon dioxide containing bromine vapour through an aqueous solution of orcin.

These two halogenated orcins readily undergo Pechmann's condensation forming substituted coumarins with acetoacetic ester or its alkyl derivatives. These substituted coumarins may be 5-hydroxy- or 7-hydroxy-coumarins according as the chloro-orcine and bromo-orcine have the alternative structures (III) or (IV).

The 7-hydroxycoumarins can be easily distinguished from 5-hydroxycoumarins by their fluorescence in alkaline solution. 7-Hydroxycoumarins (umbelliferones) are always fluorescent in alkaline solution and this property is entirely absent in the case of the 5-hydroxycoumarins. (*cf.* Collie and Chrystall, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1907, 1804; Dey, *ibid.*, 1915, 107, 1614, 1621; Chakravarti, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 407; Shah and Mehta, *ibid.*, 1936, 13, 359). The products obtained by condensing chloro- and bromo-orcine with acetoacetic ester and its alkyl derivatives have been found to give only an intense yellow solution in alkali without any fluorescence and they are, therefore, 5-hydroxycoumarins.* Chloro-orcine is, therefore, 4-chloro-orcine and bromo-orcine is 4-bromo-orcine. If they were 2-chloro- or 2-bromo-derivatives of orcin (IV) the coumarins derived from them would be 7-hydroxycoumarins exhibiting the characteristic blue fluorescence in alkaline solution.

* The coumarins derived from the halogenated orcins may be 6- or 8-halogenated derivatives and they are described in this paper as 6-halogenated coumarins.

The above conclusion has been further confirmed by condensing chloro-*orcin* with acetone dicarboxylic acid giving rise to a coumarin acetic acid (V), which when heated at 150-60° for several hours yielded a lactone (VI) with the elimination of a molecule of water.

The bromoresorcin and the halogenated *orcins* have been submitted to Simonis' reaction and as expected since they form coumarins with good yields in the presence of sulphuric acid they also form coumarins and not chromones by changing the condensing agent for phosphorus pentoxide according to Simonis. Thus the generalisation made by Chakravarti (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 9, 31) holds true in this case also. In order to study the effects of substituents in the acetoacetic ester molecule on the course of the reaction, bromoresorcin and the halogenated *orcins* have been condensed with methyl and ethyl acetoacetic esters. These condense most readily with good yields forming coumarins either in the presence of sulphuric acid (Pechmann's reaction) or phosphorus pentoxide (Simonis' reaction).

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

4-Bromoresorcin (*cf.* Zehner, *loc. cit.*).—It was obtained by boiling monobromoresorcylic acid (1 part) with water (10 parts) acidified with a few drops of dilute sulphuric acid for 16 hours. The solution was then extracted with ether, the ethereal extract washed with dilute ammonium carbonate solution, dried over calcium chloride, the ether removed, when monobromoresorcin was obtained as a solid crystalline mass, m.p. 99.5°.

6-Bromo-7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin.—To a mixture of bromoresorcin (4 g.) and acetoacetic ester (3 g.), cooled in ice, concentrated sulphuric acid (*d* 1.84, 10 c.c.) was slowly added with continuous shaking. The solution was kept overnight and poured into ice when a greyish solid separated. It was collected and crystallised from glacial acetic acid

(charcoal) as colourless prisms, m.p. 278°. (Found : Br, 31.15. $C_{10}H_7O_3Br$ requires Br, 31.36 per cent).

The *acetyl* derivative, prepared as usual by heating with acetic anhydride and sodium acetate, crystallised from dilute alcohol as colourless needles, m.p. 170°. (Found : Br, 26.82. $C_{12}H_9O_4Br$ requires Br, 26.93 per cent).

The identical compound was prepared using phosphorus pentoxide as the condensing agent (m.p. and mixed m.p. 278°; the *acetyl* derivative, m.p. 170°).

6-Bromo-7-hydroxy-3:4-dimethylcoumarin was obtained from bromoresorcin and methyl acetoacetic ester either in the presence of sulphuric acid or phosphorus pentoxide. It crystallised from glacial acetic acid as colourless silky needles, m.p. 275°. (Found : Br, 29.06. $C_{11}H_9O_3Br$ requires Br, 29.74 per cent).

The *acetyl* derivative crystallised from dilute alcohol in silky needles, m.p. 162°. (Found : Br, 25.53. $C_{13}H_{11}O_4Br$ requires Br, 25.72 per cent).

6-Bromo-7-hydroxy-4-methyl-3-ethylcoumarin from bromoresorcin and ethyl acetoacetic ester (with sulphuric acid or phosphorus pentoxide) crystallised from glacial acetic acid as colourless silky needles, m.p. 240°. (Found : Br, 27.96. $C_{12}H_{11}O_3Br$ requires Br, 28.26 per cent).

The *acetyl* derivative crystallised from dilute alcohol in colourless needles, m.p. 152°. (Found : Br, 24.28. $C_{14}H_{13}O_4Br$ requires Br, 24.62 per cent).

8-Bromo-4-methylumbelliferone.—8-Diazoanhydride-4-methylumbelliferone (7 g., Pechmann and Obermiller, *Ber.*, 1901, 34, 666) was dissolved in the least quantity of concentrated hydrobromic acid and the solution added to cuprous bromide solution (prepared by adding 150 c.c. of concentrated hydrobromic acid to 15 g. of copper carbonate and heating with copper turnings till colourless) in the cold. The reddish-brown precipitate was washed with concentrated hydrobromic acid and then with water. It was crystallised as light brown prisms from glacial acetic acid, m.p. 251-52°. (Found : Br, 31.2. $C_{10}H_7O_3Br$ requires Br, 31.37 per cent).

6-Bromo-β-methylumbelliferone Methyl Ether.—The solution of β-methylumbelliferone methyl ether-6-diazobromide, obtained from 6-amino-β-methylumbelliferone methyl ether, was added to cuprous bromide solution in the cold. The brown precipitate obtained was washed with hydrobromic acid and water and crystallised from glacial acetic acid as colourless prisms, m.p. 245°.

The identical compound was obtained by methylating the coumarin obtained by the condensation of bromoresorcin with acetoacetic ester with dimethylsulphate and alkali (m.p. and mixed m.p. 245°). (Found : Br, 29.49. $C_{11}H_9O_3$ Br requires Br, 29.74 per cent).

Preparation of 4-Bromoresorcin from Resorcin-disulphonic Acid.—Resorcin (44 g.) was heated on the water-bath with fuming sulphuric acid (15%, 85 c.c.) and concentrated sulphuric acid (d 1.84, 85 c.c.) and the precipitated disulphonic acid was collected and washed with glacial acetic acid. It was washed with benzene and the dried substance dissolved in 300 c.c. of glacial acetic acid and bromine (34 g.) added drop by drop. The solution was then diluted with water and distilled with superheated steam at 180° and the residual solution on cooling was filtered and the filtrate extracted with ether. The ethereal extract was washed with a dilute solution of ammonium carbonate and water, the ether removed and the oil was left in the desiccator when it solidified. It was crystallised from water, m.p. 99°, yield 15 g. (mixed m.p. with bromoresorcin from resorcylic acid, 99°).

The compound, thus obtained, was proved to be 4-bromoresorcin by its condensation with acetoacetic ester in the presence of sulphuric acid, m.p. 278° and the acetyl derivative melted at 170°.

It has been observed incidentally that if the disulphonic acid of resorcin is brominated with excess of bromine, a voluminous crystalline precipitate immediately separated which crystallised from glacial acetic acid as colourless needles, m.p. 111°. It has been identified to be tribromoresorcin.

Preparation of 4-Chloro-orcin.—Sulphuryl chloride (17 g.) was added drop by drop to a cooled solution of orcin (28 g.) in dry ether. At first there was little evolution of sulphur dioxide and hydrogen chloride but after some time the reaction was vigorous. The ethereal solution was washed at first with dilute sodium carbonate solution and then with water. The ether was removed and the product distilled at 138-39°/4 mm., m.p. 104°, yield 9 g. (Found : Cl, 22.68. $C_7H_7O_2Cl$ requires Cl, 22.39 per cent.).

When *anhydrous* orcin (25 g.) was chlorinated with sulphuryl chloride (20 g.) in dry ether as above the product distilled at 140-50°/5 mm. It was redistilled at 142°/5 mm., m.p. 135°, yield 12.5 g. It is probably a polychlorinated orcin.

6-Chloro-5-hydroxy-4:7-dimethylcoumarin.—It was prepared from chloroorcin and acetoacetic ester either in the presence of sulphuric acid or

phosphorus pentoxide in the usual manner. It crystallised from glacial acetic acid in colourless prisms, m.p. 264° , yield 4.5 g. (Found : Cl, 15.36. $C_{11}H_9O_3Cl$ requires Cl, 15.81 per cent).

The *acetyl* derivative crystallised from alcohol in needles, m.p. 167° . (Found : Cl, 12.82. $C_{13}H_{11}O_4Cl$ requires Cl, 13.32 per cent).

6-Chloro-5-hydroxy-3:4:7-trimethylcoumarin from chloro-orcin and methyl acetoacetic ester (in the presence of sulphuric acid or phosphorus pentoxide) crystallised from glacial acetic acid, m.p. 276° . (Found : Cl, 14.46. $C_{12}H_{11}O_3Cl$ requires Cl, 14.88 per cent).

The *acetyl* derivative crystallised from alcohol in colourless needles, m.p. 182° . (Found : Cl, 12.72. $C_{14}H_{13}O_4Cl$ requires Cl, 12.65 per cent).

6-Chloro-5-hydroxy-4:7-dimethyl-3-ethylcoumarin was obtained by condensing chloro-orcin with ethyl-acetoacetic ester in the presence of sulphuric acid or phosphorus pentoxide. It crystallised from glacial acetic acid, m.p. 210° . (Found : Cl, 14.28. $C_{13}H_{13}O_3Cl$ requires Cl, 14.06 per cent).

The *acetyl* derivative crystallised from dilute alcohol in needles, m.p. 173° . (Found : Cl, 11.68. $C_{15}H_{15}O_4Cl$ requires Cl, 12.05 per cent).

6-Chloro-5-hydroxy-7-methyl-4-acetic Acid.—This was prepared from chloroorcin, citric acid and sulphuric acid by the method of Dey and Row (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 1, 112). It crystallised from dilute alcohol as needles, m.p. 275° - 80° . (Found : Cl, 13.04. $C_{12}H_9O_5Cl$ requires Cl, 13.22 per cent).

The lactone of this acid was obtained by heating the acid at 150° - 60° for several hours. It crystallises from dilute alcohol and is insoluble in dilute sodium carbonate solution. (Found : Cl, 14.42. $C_{12}H_7O_4Cl$ requires Cl, 14.17 per cent).

Preparation of Monobromo-orcin.—A slow stream of carbon dioxide was passed through bromine (9 g.) and the carbon dioxide carrying the bromine vapour was passed into an aqueous solution of orcin (20 g. in 400 c.c. of water). The solution was filtered and on concentrating the filtrate dark brown crystals separated. It was recrystallised from water, m. p. 142° . (Found : Br, 39.48. Calc. for $C_7H_7O_2Br$: Br, 39.41 per cent).

6-Bromo-5-hydroxy-4:7-dimethylcoumarin, prepared from bromo-orcin and acetoacetic ester as usual either in the presence of sulphuric acid or

phosphorus pentoxide, crystallised from glacial acetic acid as prisms, m.p. 217°. (Found : Br, 30.04. $C_{11}H_9O_3Br$ requires Br, 29.74 per cent).

The *acetyl* derivative crystallised from dilute alcohol as needles, m.p. 197°. (Found : Br, 25.13. $C_{13}H_{11}O_4$ Br requires Br, 25.72 per cent).

6-Bromo-5-hydroxy-3:4:7-trimethylcoumarin, from bromo-orcin and methyl acetoacetic ester, crystallised from glacial acetic acid, m.p. 195°. (Found : Br, 27.63. $C_{14}H_{11}O_3Br$ requires Br, 28.26 per cent).

The *acetyl* derivative crystallised from dilute alcohol as needles, m.p. 158-59°. (Found : Br, 24.96. $C_{12}H_{13}O_4Br$ requires Br, 24.62 per cent).

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